

THE IMPORTANCE OF GAMES IN THE FORMATION OF ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Doniyorova Marjona Sarvar qizi

Student of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Gmail: marjonadoniyorova114@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: **Zubaydova Nilufar Nematillayevna**

Teacher at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Language

Abstract: This article provides information about the advantage and importance of using game methods in teaching foreign languages to elementary school students, the effectiveness of using innovative technologies in the formation of speaking skills. It is also explained how much teachers can contribute to increase the interest of young students in learning foreign languages.

Key words: English speaking skills, modern methods, primary class, game method, vocabulary, innovative technologies, methods of forming communication skills.

Today, the demand for learning and teaching foreign languages, especially English, is increasing. We know that the use of modern technologies in teaching foreign languages is useful and effective for every learner. Because nowadays learning foreign languages is very important for representatives of all fields. After all, if they learn an additional language, they will receive an increase in their monthly salary. This will motivate them to study more. I would also like to mention that there are several effective ways to teach English speaking skills to children. In particular, it is possible to show videos, dialogues, movies or cartoons or use CDs in the course of the lesson. Because listening to English speeches in any audio form will help them to speak English fluently. The use of modern technology like this ensures that the lesson is both interesting and useful. At the same time, I would like to express my opinion about the game method. In order to develop the English language, English is taught in our country from the 1st grade. This is what is said in paragraph 9 of the decision of the honorable President, " ...the preparation and broadcasting of programs on teaching foreign languages to children and teenagers through television, including local TV channels, the history and culture of other peoples of the world to ensure the regular showing of popular scientific, foreign, artistic and multiplex films devoted to science and technology with Uzbek subtitles." he said. There are 4 stages in learning foreign languages, which consist of skills such as

listening, speaking, writing and reading. The role of the game method to improve these skills is incomparable. Especially the lower grade students are very interested in game-based lessons and try to be active to participate in the game during the lesson.

At the same time, strengthening the learned topics and new topic vocabulary with the help of various interesting activities and crosswords will make students interested in the lesson. When using game methods to develop children's English speaking skills, it is appropriate for the science teacher to choose a game depending on the age and level of knowledge of the students in the class he/she is teaching. The use of this type of method ensures that the students' memory is strengthened, they become smart and agile, they work as a team, and they understand and support each other.

Games are of great importance in the formation of English speaking skills in elementary school students. Through play, students increase their interest and motivation, which makes the learning process more effective.

Interest and activity: Games attract children's attention and keep them actively involved in the learning process.

Practice language skills: Through games, students have the opportunity to actively use new words and phrases.

Teamwork: Many games are played with a team, developing children's cooperation and communication skills.

Reduce stress: Games lighten the environment, which allows students to not be afraid of making mistakes.

Management and critical thinking: Some games develop strategic thinking and decision-making skills.

For example: Role-play - a role-playing game performs speech, game and educational activities at the same time. Students play different roles in English. The purpose of the role play is to form and develop students' speaking skills. Role-playing games meet the requirements of the draft national curriculum of general secondary education because they are based on interpersonal relationships, while also stimulating students' interest in thinking and speaking in English.

In conclusion, we should mention that even the most complicated and boring grammar rules can be learned with pleasure by using games for elementary grades. If we make speaking games an integral part of our lessons, we will make students succeed in learning to understand and speak English. We should also emphasize that learning foreign languages for primary school students is the first step for their

future. It is at this time, that is, the role of parents and class leaders is important in children's language learning. Therefore, I believe that it is necessary for parents to create good conditions for their children at home, and for teachers to use modern technologies in schools to make lessons interesting. After all, children listen and learn with great interest the lessons conducted in a colorful and interesting way.

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